

Crisis of African Entity in Chinua Achebe's *Arrow of God*

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Abstract

African culture despite its richness degraded for centuries by the western hands got a fresh uplift through the writings of some important post- colonial writers. This article is a study of various measures adopted by west for the colonial subjugation and how some African writers resisted this through their writings. These writers projected the enormous rituals as a part of Africa and the trauma faced by Africans during colonialism. Arrow of God is a study of dilemma in Ezeulu’s mind during changed social order in Africa. This work is a projection of various rituals and traditions as the very essence of African entity. The article also analyzes the western notion of hegemony, how it worked against the colonized and how it forced the natives to throw away their own culture.

Keywords: hegemony, subjugation, entity, ethnicity, intellectuals, marginalization.

African culture which is rich in traditional values and culture has made us aware of the literary world by the writings of Chinua Achebe. The first step in this attempt is *Things Fall Apart* (1958). It is about the collapsing of world order felt by the protagonist as a result of foreign influence. The next one is *Arrow of God* (1964). It is a psychological study about a leader’s mind which is deeply involved in Igbo traditional entity. Achebe who is a veteran in showing the minute details of Igbo society, does not disappoint the readers of *Arrow of God* (1964). Achebe here shows identity crisis of Ezeulu who is a priest. This crisis is actually, an inner conflict in Ezeulu’s mind whether his culture would survive in the colonial occupation. The novel is also a redefining of powers and roles of a priest whose relation with people gradually changed due to foreign influence. The metaphor of mask in the novel is used to justify Ezeulu’s decision to send his son to colonial school. But in reality the mask shows his dual personality. On one side he hides his own self. And on the other side, he tries to fix his authority on his people in the wake of changed social power equations.

The novel is really a struggle of a common man, a priest and a father, to sustain in his religion and tradition. He has felt like the power of Ulu is questioned who is not able to save his people from white man. In dream he has seen that some people spit on his face and call him the priest of a dead god. Ezeulu is not ready to accept the new social order in which his Ulu has no role. His mind is wandering

with the present state of disorder. Ezeulu is also irritated that his religious doctrines and priestly hood are in the point of a threat. At the beginning of the novel strife happens on a piece of land. This conflict gradually becomes a question of authority and a weapon in the hand of foreigners to establish their authority and religion.

The novel intrigues into the faith of one person and his efforts to assert its importance. For Ezeulu, Ulu is the supreme truth in this world. So when all others in the village started to question the tradition and the age old Gods, the chief priest remained unmoved in his faith. But the colonial powers made such a trick that the belief and authority all are questioned through other natives like Nwaka. Here most importantly, the colonists attempt to question the African authority in African terms. They have exercised their power only through African converts and not directly with white people. It is the age old white attempt to control the Orient mind through English language and religion which Ezeulu tired to provoke.

A close connection is observed between the writings of Ngugi Wa Thiongo, Fanon, Edward Said and Achebe that the method of oppression of the colonized is through linguistic domination. The colonizer is well aware of the fact that only through their language, they can have control over colonised people. Here Chinua like Thiongo expresses his concern over Semiotics. The interpretations of Igbo culture made by foreigners are far different from actuality. This confusion gradually resulted in confusion of life for African people. The important attempt of Achbe through this novel is not to express a world of derailed order. But conveys how rich and unique Igbo tradition is made value less by its own people. Through this white were able to question the very existence of an age old tradition. They also tried to give their own meaning to the Igbo signs.

Though westerners succeeded in their socio cultural oppression, they faced strong resistance from Africa itself. The writers who initiated an intellectual protest in western language were Fanon, Edward Said, Chinua Achebe, Thiongo etc. Thiongo has made an exception by writing in his own Gikuyu language. He considers it as a protest and felt that African literature can survive only through regional language. But the most striking aspect is their reluctance to involve with those African intellectuals that after English education started writing in terms with Western interests. Such pseudo African writers showed in their writings the enormous African ritual and traditions as a cause of African backwardness. But on the other hand Chinua and Thiongo projected this as the essence of Africa. Okonkwo and Ezeulu are the paramount declaration of African ethnicity. The psychological confusion faced by both the characters show the trauma faced by each African during imperialism.

In the words of Simon Gikandi, *Arrow of God* (1964) represents a struggle of power and authority between Africa and colonial tradition. The figure of dancing mask shows the various interpretation of Igbo aesthetic. He opines that *Arrow of God* shows the relationship between tradition and change. In Gikandi's work 'Reading Chinua Achebe' (1991) he says that many tensions in Umuaro can be related to one simple question:

“where do the allegiances of different characters and social groups lie when important ritual acts cannot guarantee security and continuity?” (53). Here the metaphor of mask is used to show the intensity of tension between tradition and transformation. Similarly *Arrow of God* shows a tug-of-war in the consciousness of Africans as experienced by Derek Walcott. Here Derek also pictures in his work *A Far Cry from Africa* (1962) a sense of disorientation and homelessness. Both Derek and Chinua feel that home lies in any direction away from the region. Both the works show a sense of insecurity which Derek writes in “*A Far Cry from Africa*. I who am poisoned with the blood of both. Where shall I turn, divided to the vein?” (6)

According to Chinweizu, an eminent Nigerian critic, African literature has an autonomous entity and so its models and norms are unique. Those are related to Africa must be different from Europe.

But, the West failed to understand this uniqueness. An important acknowledgement in this respect is Frantz Fanon's *The Wretched of the Earth* (1961). Here he says that "blackness" is a western constructed synonym for unprivileged, poverty, backwardness etc. he came to such a conclusion from his experiences as a psychiatrist. He has noticed the treatment of North African patients by French doctors during Algerian war of independence. Those who have come with physical ailment are considered as psychologically affected. Here the patient fails to understand the questions of doctors and they do not ask the right questions. Fanon feels that the colonized experience and language are denied. This results in their marginalization and subjugation.

The emotional sensitivity of the native is kept on the surface of his skin like an open sore which flinches from the caustic agent: and the psyche shrinks back, obliterates itself and finds outlet in muscular demonstrations which have caused certain wise men to say that the native is a hysterical type. (15)

Another important writer in the post colonial resistance is Edward Said. The most important work of Said is *Orientalism* (1978). This book describes the western notion of Orient or East (people of Asia and Africa) as inferior. The western sponsored scholars who study the languages of the orient did not consider them as subject but as an unchanging, uniform and peculiar object. In Said's opinion this is "the Orientalist hegemonic attitude" and condemns it. He has given many analyses in this topic like his comments on Mansfield Park and Heart of Darkness. Said set more examples for this lowering of orient culture. For example Disraeli wrote during his trip to Cairo that his eyes and mind yet ache with grandeur so little in unison with our own likeness. Such Orientalist attitude is revealed in the works of Goethe, Hugo, Scott, Byron, George Eliot etc. The success of Orientalism depended upon the success of imperialism and colonialism. But in the twentieth century this concept faced and facing a threat in the wake of the uprising of post- colonial orient.

As above mentioned west pictured all those which are beyond their understanding as inferior. This contrast is evident from an attempt to kill the Royal Python in the novel. The old priest Ezeulu at first decided to send his sons to missionary school and he sent his son Oduche there. There he by the influence of John Goodcountry decided to kill a python which is considered sacred by the Africans. Here we see the deliberate attack on African culture and they are taught that if they have to remain as Christians they must kill Python.

Ezeulu's son is brainwashed to kill a sacred python to get rid of the disturbance made by it. Python is actually there always in his hut without making any problem to anyone. In fact it is the act of the boy that has resulted in the argument between Ezeulu and one of a messenger sent by Ediemili. Ezeulu is actually very much annoyed by his son's act. He knows that it is against their culture. Ezeulu has sent his son to church in the expectation that it would make his son fit for this new and changing world- "The world is like a Mask dancing. If you want to see it well you do not stand in one place. My spirit tells me that those who do not befriend the white man today will be saying had we known tomorrow." (46).

Here we see the fascination of Africans towards English and English culture. Oduche who is at first reluctant to go to church gradually inspired by Blackett, a West Indian missionary. He is considered more knowledgeable than whites. Another teacher called John Goodcountry comes there and he is the best example for planned attack on orient culture. John Goodcountry tells converts of Umara about the early Christians who have fought against bad customs of their people and how they destroyed shrines. Those who destroyed traditional signs are given martyrdom. John Goodcountry said "you must be ready to kill the python as the people of the rivers killed the iguana. You address the python as Father. It is nothing but a snake, the snake that deceived out first mother, Eve" (38).

Arrow of God is thus an excellent effort to show how colonial interest plans their attack on colonies. How African entity is thrashed and how it became priceless before its own people.

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